

Key Services of the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) for German Office Buildings

Practice-Oriented Implementation with Graphical Representation and Combination Options

within the project

“Classification and quantitative Assessment of Data Infrastructure and Control Options in
Typified Simulations for Possible Adaptation of the Smart Readiness Indicator”
(German Acronym: Klassiqua)

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1 Identification of 15 SRI key services for German office buildings in the Klassiqua Project

Smart technologies are considered to make a significant contribution to achieving climate protection targets in the building sector. The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), developed by the European Commission, aims to promote the expansion of intelligent building technology. It assesses a building's ability to interact with its occupants and the grid, thereby enabling energy-efficient operation. In this context, the SRI indicates the degree to which technical prerequisites for the implementation of smart operating strategies are fulfilled. Setpoints (e.g. temperatures, comfort classes, or time schedules) for these operating strategies are not defined. EU Member States are called upon to implement the SRI at national level and to introduce it as mandatory for large non-residential buildings from mid-2027.¹

In the Klassiqua research project, together with construction industry partners from the fields of planning, construction, and monitoring, the effects of investment scenarios aimed at improving the SRI rating on energy demand and thermal comfort in existing or new office buildings are investigated, as well as which investment scenarios yield economically viable projections.

The project consortium consists of Recognizer Group, Carpus+Partner, and enervision, as well as the Institute for Energy Efficient Buildings and Indoor Climate (EBC) at RWTH Aachen University. The quantification of effects is carried out for representative SRI measure packages through annual simulations using office building archetypes.

The current SRI draft (Calculation Sheet Version 4.5)² encompasses nine technical domains and 54 services. Within the Klassiqua project, the benefits with regard to energy efficiency and thermal comfort resulting from SRI improvement measures are investigated in particular.

In the context of German office buildings, the project consortium assesses the technical domains of *Heating, Cooling, Ventilation, Dynamic Envelope (solar shading), and Monitoring and Control (of building operation)* as the primary areas of influence. By means of pairwise comparison of the services listed therein, 15 key services were identified. These are presented in Table 1.1. The first part of the SRI code refers to the English designation of the corresponding technical domain:

- H - Heating
- C - Cooling
- V - Ventilation
- DE - Dynamic Envelope
- MC - Monitoring and Control

¹European Union (2024): Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings.

²European Commission (ed.) (2023): Assessment Package Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI). Available online at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/SRI-assessment-package>

The subsequent numerals and, in some cases, lower-case letters correspond to the internal SRI numbering.

Table 1.1: Overview of the identified SRI key services for German office buildings in the Klassiqua project

SRI code	SRI service description
H-1a	Heat emission control
H-1b	Emission control for TABS* (heating mode)
H-2a	Heat generator control (all except heat pumps)
H-2b	Heat generator control (for heat pumps)
C-1a	Cooling emission control
C-1b	Emission control for TABS* (cooling mode)
C-1f	Interlock: avoiding simultaneous heating and cooling in the same room
C-2a	Generator control for cooling
V-1a	Supply air flow control at the room level
V-1c	Air flow or pressure control at the air handler level
V-2d	Supply air temperature control at the air handling unit level
DE-1	Window solar shading control
MC-4	Detecting faults of technical building systems and providing support to the diagnosis of these faults
MC-13	Central reporting of TBS** performance and energy use
MC-30	Single platform that allows automated control & coordination between TBS + optimisation of energy flow based on occupancy, weather and grid signals

*TABS = thermally activated building systems; **TBS = technical building system

2 Explanatory notes on the content of this publication

This publication presents the 15 SRI key services identified for German office buildings. Each service comprises three to five functional levels. The level under consideration is indicated in parentheses after the SRI code of the service.

The SRI descriptions are taken from the *Calculation Sheet Version 4.5*³. Only small spelling and punctuation errors have been corrected. It is hereby stated that the present publication employs British English. In large parts, the current SRI draft is based on existing content from *EN 15232*⁴ and its following standard *EN ISO 52120*⁵. Not all functions and levels listed in the standard are included in the SRI, and vice versa.

With the aim to deepen the understanding of the SRI descriptions, relevant matching functions and descriptions from *English translation of DIN EN ISO 52120*⁶ are additionally referenced, in some cases in abbreviated form.

On the basis of the descriptions, the Klassiqua project consortium has formulated typical implementations of the SRI levels. These are accompanied by simplified technical drawings illustrating the relevant components and communication pathways. The practice-oriented implementation solution shows typical (minimum) configurations. Alternative implementation options exist.

The emission systems are always illustrated using two rooms forming a zone as an example. In practice, zones may also encompass other configurations. Likewise, in the domain of ventilation, rooms served exclusively by supply air or extract air may exist.

Service C-1a „Cooling emission control“ is primarily designed for the assessment of central cooling systems. In view of the increasing retrofitting of local split air-conditioning units in existing buildings, the project consortium also considers this service in a supplementary decentralised variant. Services H-2b „Heat generator control (for heat pumps)“ and C-2a „Generator control for cooling“ describe an output control that nevertheless requires a temperature setpoint. For this reason, an outdoor-temperature-compensated supply temperature setpoint has been assumed, corresponding to the heating case H-2a (1). The practice-oriented implementations are followed by overviews of technically suitable, feasible or unsuitable combinations of the presented SRI service levels on the emission and generation side, as assessed by the project consortium..

³European Commission (Ed.) (2023): Assessment Package Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI). Available online at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/SRI-assessment-package>

⁴EN 15232-1:2017. Energy Performance of Buildings. Part 1: Impact of Building Automation, Controls and Building Management

⁵DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2022. Energy Performance of Buildings. Contribution of building automation, controls and building management. Part 1: General framework and procedures

⁶English translation of DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02. Energy performance of buildings. Contribution of building automation, controls and building management. Part 1: General framework and procedures

3 Key service descriptions according to SRI and DIN and practice-oriented implementation with schematic diagrams

Table 3.1: Symbols and abbreviations used

Actuators	Automation	HVAC Components - Continuation
manual straight-through valve	controller	air conditioning split units
thermostatic control valve	constant setpoint	thermally active building systems
motorized straight-through valve	heating or cooling curve	sunshade with motor
motorized mixing valve	time profile	
exhaust air outlet	timer switch	
supply air outlet	presence detector with switching contact	
variable flow air terminal unit	building automation	Further Abbreviations
constant flow air terminal unit with actuator	building management system	AHU air handling unit
heating or cooling coil	alarm management module	ATU air terminal unit
pump	weather forecast	AUTO automatic operation
fan or compressor one-stage adjustable	grid signals	BA building automation
fan or compressor two-stage adjustable	diagnostic function	BACS building automation and control system
fan or compressor continuously adjustable	technical building system	C cooling
	energy meter	CO ₂ carbon dioxide
Sensors	report	EHA exhaust air
temperature sensor	unidirectional signal	EMS energy management system
pressure sensor	bidirectional signal	ETA extracted air
air quality sensor		H heating
outdoor temperature sensor		HVAC heating, ventilation, air conditioning
room temperature sensor	HVAC Components	Imp Implementation
room air quality sensor	pipes, ducts, or cables	MANU manual operation
presence detector	radiator	ODA outdoor air
daylight sensor	cooling ceiling	OT outdoor temperature
manual switch	lighting	SUP supply air
		TABS thermally active building systems
		TBS technical building system
		VFD variable frequency drive
		VOC volatile organic compounds
		WR water return (heating/cooling)
		WS water supply (heating/cooling)

Table 3.2: SRI Service H-1a, Heat emission control (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 1.1), Imp = Practice-Oriented Implementation

H-1a Level 0	SRI	No automatic control	
	DIN	No automatic control of the room temperature	
	Imp	No control available (on/off)	
H-1a Level 1	SRI	Central automatic control (e.g. central thermostat)	
	DIN	Central automatic control [...] acting either on the distribution or on the generation. Function is to be integrated in a system.	
	Imp	No control at room level; outdoor temperature-based adjustment of supply temperature at generator (prerequisite min. H-2a (1))	
H-1a Level 2	SRI	Individual room control (e.g. thermostatic valves, or electronic controller)	
	DIN	Individual room control: by thermostatic valves or electronic controller	
	Imp	Room-level control via thermostatic control valve to fixed, constant setpoint	
H-1a Level 3	SRI	Individual room control with communication between controllers and to BACS	
	DIN	Individual modulating room control with communication: between controllers and BACS (e.g. scheduler, room temperature setpoint)	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control; communication to higher-level building automation system for setpoint profile transfer	
H-1a Level 4	SRI	Individual room control with communication and occupancy detection	
	DIN	Individual modulating room control with communication and occupancy detection: between controllers and BACS; demand control/occupancy detection [...]	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control; occupancy detection with presence sensor; occupancy-dependent setpoint profiles; communication to higher-level building automation system	

Table 3.3: SRI Service H-1b, Emission control for TABS (heating mode) (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 1.2)

H-1b Level 0	SRI	No automatic control	
	DIN	No automatic control of the room temperature	
	Imp	No control available (on/off)	
H-1b Level 1	SRI	Central automatic control	
	DIN	Central automatic control [...] for a TABS zone [...] typically is a supply water temperature control loop whose set-point is dependent on the filtered outside temperature [...].	
	Imp	Adjustment of supply temperature depending on outdoor temperature at zone level via mixing valve	
H-1b Level 2	SRI	Advanced central automatic control	
	DIN	Advanced central automatic control [...] of the TABS zone that is designed and tuned to achieve an optimal self-regulating [...].	
	Imp	Adjustment of supply temperature depending on outdoor temperature at zone level via mixing valve; use of time profiles (setpoint supply temperature) for optimisation of self-regulation effect	
H-1b Level 3	SRI	Advanced central automatic control with intermittent operation and/or room temperature feedback control	
	DIN	[...] The pump is switched off regularly to save electrical energy [...] [and/or] the supply water temperature set-point is corrected by the output of a room temperature feedback controller [...].	
	Imp	Adjustment of supply temperature depending on outdoor temperature at zone level via mixing valve; correction of setpoint via room temperature trend	

Table 3.4: SRI Service H-2a, Heat generator control (all except heat pumps) (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 1.6)

H-2a Level 0	SRI	Constant temperature control	
	DIN	Constant temperature control	
	Imp	Constant setpoint supply temperature at heat generator	
H-2a Level 1	SRI	Variable temperature control depending on outdoor temperature	
	DIN	Variable temperature control depending on outside temperature	
	Imp	Outdoor temperature-based adjustment of setpoint supply temperature	
H-2a Level 2	SRI	Variable temperature control depending on the load (e.g. depending on supply water temperature set point)	
	DIN	Variable temperature control depending on the load: e.g. depending on supply water temperature set point	
	Imp	Outdoor temperature-based adjustment of setpoint supply temperature; correction of setpoint by considering the spread (supply/return)	

Table 3.5: SRI Service H-2b, Heat generator control (for heat pumps) (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 1.8)

H-2b Level 0	SRI	On/Off-control of heat generator	
	DIN	On/off-control of heat generator	
	Imp	Heat pump with single-speed compressor; part-load operation through compressor cycling; supply temperature control with outdoor temperature-dependent setpoint (cf. H-2a (1))	
H-2b Level 1	SRI	Multi-stage control of heat generator capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. on/off of several compressors)	
	DIN	Multi-stage control of heat generator capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. on/off of several compressors)	
	Imp	Heat pump with multiple compressors switched on according to capacity demand; supply temperature control with outdoor temperature-dependent setpoint (cf. H-2a (1))	
H-2b Level 2	SRI	Variable control of heat generator capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. hot gas bypass, inverter frequency control)	
	DIN	Variable control of heat generator capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. hot gas bypass, inverter frequency control)	
	Imp	Heat pump with variable-speed compressor; speed adjustment to capacity demand; supply temperature control with outdoor temperature-dependent setpoint (cf. H-2a (1))	
H-2b Level 3	SRI	Variable control of heat generator capacity depending on the load AND external signals from grid	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Heat pump with variable-speed compressor; speed adjustment to capacity demand and grid signals via receiver interface (blocking, dimming, start-up)	

Table 3.6: SRI Service C-1a, Cooling emission control, Note: Primarily for the evaluation of central systems (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 3.1)

C-1a Level 0	SRI	No automatic control	
	DIN	No automatic control of the room temperature	
	Imp	No control available (on/off)	
C-1a Level 1	SRI	Central automatic control	
	DIN	Central automatic control [...] acting either on the distribution or on the generation. Function is to be integrated in a system.	
	Imp	No control at room level; outdoor temperature-based adjustment of supply temperature at generator	
C-1a Level 2	SRI	Individual room control	
	DIN	Individual room control: by thermostatic valves or electronic controller	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control to constant setpoint	
C-1a Level 3	SRI	Individual room control with communication between controllers and to BACS	
	DIN	Individual modulating room control with communication: between controllers and BACS (e.g. scheduler, room temperature setpoint)	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control; communication to higher-level building automation system for setpoint profile transfer	
C-1a Level 4	SRI	Individual room control with communication and occupancy detection	
	DIN	Individual modulating room control with communication and occupancy detection: between controllers and BACS; demand control/occupancy detection [...]	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control; occupancy detection with presence sensor; occupancy-dependent setpoint profiles; communication to higher-level building automation system	

Table 3.7: SRI Service C-1a, Cooling emission control, here: alternative perspective on decentralised systems (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 3.1)

C-1a_decentralised Level 0	SRI	No automatic control	
	DIN	No automatic control of the room temperature	
	Imp	No control available (on/off)	
C-1a_decentralised Level 1	SRI	Central automatic control	<p>No implementation for decentralized systems.</p>
	DIN	Central automatic control [...] acting either on the distribution or on the generation. Function is to be integrated in a system.	
	Imp	[No implementation for decentralised systems.]	
C-1a_decentralised Level 2	SRI	Individual room control	
	DIN	Individual room control: by thermostatic valves or electronic controller	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control to constant setpoint	
C-1a_decentralised Level 3	SRI	Individual room control with communication between controllers and to BACS	
	DIN	Individual modulating room control with communication: between controllers and BACS (e.g. scheduler, room temperature setpoint)	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control; communication to higher-level building automation system for setpoint profile transfer	
C-1a_decentralised Level 4	SRI	Individual room control with communication and occupancy detection	
	DIN	Individual modulating room control with communication and occupancy detection: between controllers and BACS; demand control/occupancy detection [...]	
	Imp	Motorised valve and room sensor for room temperature control; occupancy detection with presence sensor; occupancy-dependent setpoint profiles; communication to higher-level building automation system	

Table 3.8: SRI Service C-1b, Emission control for TABS (cooling mode) (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 3.2)

C-1b Level 0	SRI	No automatic control	
	DIN	No automatic control of the room temperature	
	Imp	No control available	
C-1b Level 1	SRI	Central automatic control	
	DIN	Central automatic control [...] for a TABS zone [...] typically is a supply water temperature control loop whose set-point is dependent on the filtered outside temperature [...].	
	Imp	Adjustment of supply temperature depending on outdoor temperature at zone level via mixing valve	
C-1b Level 2	SRI	Advanced central automatic control	
	DIN	Advanced central automatic control [...] of the TABS zone that is designed and tuned to achieve an optimal self-regulating [...].	
	Imp	Adjustment of supply temperature depending on outdoor temperature at zone level via mixing valve; use of time profiles (setpoint supply temperature) for optimisation of self-regulation effect	
C-1b Level 3	SRI	Advanced central automatic control with intermittent operation and/or room temperature feedback control	
	DIN	[...] The pump is switched off regularly to save electrical energy [...] [and/or] the supply water temperature set-point is corrected by the output of a room temperature feedback controller [...].	
	Imp	Adjustment of supply temperature depending on outdoor temperature at zone level via mixing valve; correction of setpoint via room temperature trend	

Table 3.9: SRI Service C-1f, Interlock: avoiding simultaneous heating and cooling in the same room (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 3.6)

C-1f Level 0	SRI	No interlock	
	DIN	No interlock: the two systems are controlled independently and can provide simultaneously heating and cooling.	
	Imp	No interlock	
C-1f Level 1	SRI	Partial interlock (minimising risk of simultaneous heating and cooling e.g. by sliding setpoints)	
	DIN	Partial interlock (depending on the HVAC system): [...] minimize the possibility of simultaneous heating and cooling. [...] defining a sliding setpoint for the supply temperature of the centrally controlled system.	
	Imp	Heating and cooling curves, or the limit temperatures respectively, are set far enough apart that simultaneous heating and cooling in rooms is unlikely.	
C-1f Level 2	SRI	Total interlock (control system ensures no simultaneous heating and cooling can take place)	
	DIN	Total interlock: the control function enables to guarantee that there will be no simultaneous heating and cooling.	
	Imp	Simultaneous operation of systems is prevented by mechanical interlock (changeover valve).	

Table 3.10: SRI Service C-2a, Generator control for cooling (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 3.7)

C-2a Level 0	SRI	On/Off-control of cooling production	
	DIN	Constant temperature control	
	Imp	Chiller with single-speed compressor; part-load operation through compressor cycling; supply temperature control with outdoor temperature-dependent setpoint (cf. H-2a (1))	
C-2a Level 1	SRI	Multi-stage control of cooling production capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. on/off of several compressors)	
	DIN	Variable temperature control depending on the outside temperature	
	Imp	Chiller with multiple compressors switched on according to capacity demand; supply temperature control with outdoor temperature-dependent setpoint (cf. H-2a (1))	
C-2a Level 2	SRI	Variable control of cooling production capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. hot gas bypass, inverter frequency control)	
	DIN	Variable temperature control depending on the load: this includes control according to room temperature.	
	Imp	Chiller with variable-speed compressor; speed adjustment to capacity demand; supply temperature control with outdoor temperature-dependent setpoint (cf. H-2a (1))	
C-2a Level 3	SRI	Variable control of cooling production capacity depending on the load AND external signals from grid	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Chiller with variable-speed compressor; speed adjustment to capacity demand and grid signals via receiver interface (blocking, dimming, start-up)	

Table 3.11: SRI Service V-1a, Supply air flow control at the room level (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 4.1)

V-1a Level 0	SRI	No ventilation system or manual control	
	DIN	No automatic control: the system runs constantly (e.g. manual controlled switch).	
	Imp	No air volume flow control at room level	
V-1a Level 1	SRI	Clock control	
	DIN	Time control: the system runs according to a given time schedule.	
	Imp	Tight-closing constant air volume controller per zone with actuator controlled by time switch (closed or constant air volume)	
V-1a Level 2	SRI	Occupancy detection control	
	DIN	Occupancy based control: the system runs dependent on the occupancy (presence, light switch, infrared sensors etc.).	
	Imp	Tight-closing constant air volume controller per zone with actuator controlled by presence sensor (closed or constant air volume)	
V-1a Level 3	SRI	Central Demand Control based on air quality sensors (CO ₂ , VOC, humidity, ...)	
	DIN	Demand based control: the system runs dependent on the air quality demand (measurement of CO ₂ , VOC, etc.).	
	Imp	Variable air volume controller per zone; air volume flow control based on air quality setpoint in zone exhaust air	
V-1a Level 4	SRI	Local Demand Control based on air quality sensors (CO ₂ , VOC,...) with local flow from/to the zone regulated by dampers	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Variable air volume controller per room; air volume flow control based on air quality setpoint in room	

Table 3.12: SRI Service V-1c, Air flow or pressure control at the air handler level (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 4.5)

V-1c Level 0	SRI	No automatic control: Continuously supplies of air flow for a maximum load of all rooms	
	DIN	No automatic control: continuously supplies air flow for a maximum load of all rooms.	
	Imp	Fan with manual switch, always in operation	
V-1c Level 1	SRI	On off time control: Continuously supplies of air flow for a maximum load of all rooms during nominal occupancy time	
	DIN	On off time control: continuously supplies air flow for a maximum load of all rooms during nominal occupancy time.	
	Imp	Fan controlled by time switch; constant capacity during defined occupancy hours	
V-1c Level 2	SRI	Multi-stage control: To reduce the auxiliary energy demand of the fan	
	DIN	Multi-stage control: to reduce the auxiliary energy demand of the fan	
	Imp	Fan with at least two speed stages; control via multi-stage time profile; part-load during periods of known lower occupancy	
V-1c Level 3	SRI	Automatic flow or pressure control without pressure reset: Load dependent supplies of air flow for the demand of all connected rooms.	
	DIN	Automatic flow or pressure control without pressure reset: load dependent supplies of air flow for the demand of all connected rooms	
	Imp	Variable-speed fan; control to pressure setpoint in duct network	
V-1c Level 4	SRI	Automatic flow or pressure control with pressure reset: Load dependent supplies of air flow for the demand of all connected rooms (for variable air volume systems with VFD).	
	DIN	Automatic flow or pressure control with pressure reset: load dependent supplies of air flow for the demand of all connected rooms (for variable air volume systems with VFD)	
	Imp	Variable-speed fan; control to pressure setpoint in duct network; pressure setpoint adjustment to demand (based on damper position of air volume controllers)	

Table 3.13: SRI Service V-2d, Supply air temperature control at the air handling unit level (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 4.9)

V-2d Level 0	SRI	No automatic control	
	DIN	No automatic control: no control loop enables to act on the supply air temperature.	
	Imp	No supply air temperature control	
V-2d Level 1	SRI	Constant setpoint: A control loop enables to control the supply air_x000D_ temperature, the setpoint is constant and can only be modified by a manual_x000D_ action	
	DIN	Constant setpoint: a control loop enables to control the supply air temperature, the setpoint is constant and can only be modified by a manual action.	
	Imp	Supply air temperature control to constant setpoint	
V-2d Level 2	SRI	Variable set point with outdoor temperature compensation	
	DIN	Variable setpoint with outside temperature compensation: a control loop enables to control the supply air temperature. The setpoint is a simple function of the outside temperature [...].	
	Imp	Supply air temperature control to setpoint dependent on outdoor temperature (heating/cooling curve)	
V-2d Level 3	SRI	Variable set point with load dependant compensation. A control loop enables to control the supply air temperature. The setpoint is defined as a function of the loads in the room	
	DIN	Variable setpoint with load dependent compensation: [...] The setpoint is defined as a function of the loads in the room. [...] collect the temperatures or actuator position in the different rooms.	
	Imp	Supply air temperature control to setpoint adjusted to room demand (room temperature feedback)	

Table 3.14: SRI Service DE-1, Window solar shading control (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 6.1)

DE-1 Level 0	SRI	No sun shading or only manual operation	
	DIN	Manual operation: mostly used only for manual shadowing, energy saving depends only on the user behaviour.	
	Imp	Manual solar shading	
DE-1 Level 1	SRI	Motorized operation with manual control	
	DIN	Motorized operation with manual control: mostly used only for easiest manual (motor supported) shadowing, energy saving depends only on the user behaviour.	
	Imp	Motorised solar shading with manual control	
DE-1 Level 2	SRI	Motorized operation with automatic control based on sensor data	
	DIN	Motorized operation with automatic control: automatic controlled dimming to reduce cooling energy.	
	Imp	Solar shading control depending on solar irradiation	
DE-1 Level 3	SRI	Combined light/blind/HVAC control	
	DIN	Combined light/blind/HVAC control: to optimize energy use for HVAC, blind and lighting for occupied and non-occupied rooms.	
	Imp	Solar shading control depending on solar irradiation; detection of presence and illuminance; constant light control of lighting; transmission of sensor data to HVAC systems	
DE-1 Level 4	SRI	Predictive blind control (e.g. based on weather forecast)	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Solar shading control depending on solar irradiation and weather forecast; detection of presence and illuminance; constant light control; transmission of sensor data and forecasts to HVAC systems	

Table 3.15: SRI Service MC-4, Detecting faults of technical building systems and providing support to the diagnosis of these faults (DIN EN ISO 52120-1:2025-02, Table 5, Row 7.3)

MC-4 Level 0	SRI	No central indication of detected faults and alarms	
	DIN	No central indication of detected faults and alarms	
	Imp	Fault and alarm display in embedded firmware only	
MC-4 Level 1	SRI	With central indication of detected faults and alarms for at least 2 relevant TBS	
	DIN	With central indication of detected faults and alarms	
	Imp	Alarm management module for at least 2 TBS with central collection, visualisation, storage and reporting of faults and alarms	
MC-4 Level 2	SRI	With central indication of detected faults and alarms for all relevant TBS	
	DIN	With central indication of detected faults and alarms including diagnosing functions	
	Imp	Alarm management module for all TBS with central collection, visualisation, storage and reporting of faults and alarms	
MC-4 Level 3	SRI	With central indication of detected faults and alarms for all relevant TBS, including diagnosing functions	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Alarm management module for all TBS with collection, visualisation, storage and reporting of alarms; diagnostic software for time series and correlation analysis	

Table 3.16: SRI Service MC-13, Central reporting of TBS performance and energy use

MC-13 Level 0	SRI	-	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Meter without communication interface	
MC-13 Level 1	SRI	Central or remote reporting of real-time energy use per energy carrier	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Communicative energy meters (wireless/wired) with online EMS service for all energy carrier connections (e.g. electricity and gas)	
MC-13 Level 2	SRI	Central or remote reporting of real-time energy use per energy carrier, combining TBS of at least 2 domains in one interface	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Communicative energy meters for at least 2 TBS connected to central energy management software (EMS) (additionally e.g. heating and ventilation)	
MC-13 Level 3	SRI	Central or remote reporting of real-time energy use per energy carrier, combining TBS of all main domains in one interface	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Communicative energy meters for all TBS connected to central energy management software (EMS)	

Table 3.17: Single platform that allows automated control & coordination between TBS + optimization of energy flow based on occupancy, weather and grid signals

MC-30 Level 0	SRI	-	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	No platform	
MC-30 Level 1	SRI	Single platform that allows manual control of multiple TBS	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Basic automation software with operating functions for all TBS	
MC-30 Level 2	SRI	Single platform that allows automated control & coordination between TBS	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Central management system (building management system, BMS) for all TBS	
MC-30 Level 3	SRI	Single platform that allows automated control & coordination between TBS + optimization of energy flow based on occupancy, weather and grid signals	
	DIN	-	
	Imp	Extended central management system (BMS) with cloud connectivity for all TBS	

4 Combination options for SRI key services

Table 4.1: Combination options: H-1a, Heat emission control <> H-2a, Heat generator control (all except heat pumps)

	H-1a (0)	H-1a (1)	H-1a (2)	H-1a (3)	H-1a (4)
H-2a (0)	o	o	o	-	-
H-2a (1)	o	+	+	o	-
H-2a (2)	-	-	+	+	+

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

H-1a (0)			
H-1a (1)			
H-1a (2)			
H-1a (3)			
H-1a (4)			

Table 4.2: Combination options: H-1b, Emission control for TABS (heating mode) <> H-2a, Heat generator control (all except heat pumps)

	H-1b (0)	H-1b (1)	H-1b (2)	H-1b (3)
H-2a (0)	o	o	o	-
H-2a (1)	o	o	o	o
H-2a (2)	-	-	-	o

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

Table 4.3: Combination options: H-1a, Heat emission control <> H-2b, Heat generator control (for heat pumps)

	H-1a (0)	H-1a (1)	H-1a (2)	H-1a (3)	H-1a (4)
H-2b (0)	o	o	o	-	-
H-2b (1)	o	o	+	+	o
H-2b (2)	o	o	o	+	+
H-2b (3)	o	o	o	+	+

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

Table 4.4: Combination options: H-1b, Emission control for TABS (heating mode) <> H-2b, Heat generator control (for heat pumps)

	H-1b (0)	H-1b (1)	H-1b (2)	H-1b (3)
H-2b (0)	o	o	o	-
H-2b (1)	+	+	+	o
H-2b (2)	+	+	+	+
H-2b (3)	o	o	o	+

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

Table 4.5: Combination options: C-1a, Cooling emission control <> C-2a, Generator control for cooling

	C-1a (0)	C-1a (1)	C-1a (2)	C-1a (3)	C-1a (4)
C-2a (0)	o	o	o	-	-
C-2a (1)	-	-	+	+	+
C-2a (2)	-	-	+	+	+
C-2a (3)	-	-	+	+	+

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

Table 4.6: Combination options: C-1b, Emission control for TABS (cooling mode) <> C-2a, Generator control for cooling

	C-1b (0)	C-1b (1)	C-1b (2)	C-1b (3)
C-2a (0)	o	o	o	-
C-2a (1)	-	o	+	+
C-2a (2)	-	o	o	+
C-2a (3)	-	o	o	+

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

Table 4.7: Combination options: V-1a, Supply air flow control at the room level <> V-1c, Air flow or pressure control at the air handler level

	V-1a (0)	V-1a (1)	V-1a (2)	V-1a(3)	V-1a (4)
V-1c (0)	+	o	-	-	-
V-1c (1)	+	+	-	-	-
V-1c (2)	-	-	+	o	o
V-1c (3)	-	-	+	+	+
V-1c (4)	-	-	+	+	+

Legend

- technically unsuitable
- o technically feasible
- + technically suitable

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

Table 4.8: Combination options: MC-4, Detecting faults of technical building systems and providing support to the diagnosis of these faults <> MC-30, Single platform that allows automated control & coordination between TBS + optimisation of energy flow based on occupancy, weather and grid signals

	MC-30 (0)	MC-30 (1)	MC-30 (2)	MC-30 (3)	Legend
MC-4 (0)	+	o	o	-	
MC-4 (1)	o	+	+	+	o technically feasible
MC-4 (2)	-	-	+	+	+ technically suitable
MC-4 (3)	-	-	+	+	

Schematic diagrams for the listed service levels

